

NANOSTRUCTURED ‘SKIN’ FOR MECHANICAL SENSING

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ABSTRACT

A simple overlapping nanoparticle method based on fibre oriented capillary flow for depositing Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) onto electrically insulating glass fibre surface to form an continuous electrically conducting skin. The multilayer architecture makes the GNP-glass fibre show structure colour. By integrating the optic performance and piezoresistive behaviour, the GNP-glass fibre embedded in epoxy matrix realise the *in-situ* sensing mechanical deformation of composite. Furthermore, both the structure colour tuning and the resistance changing with the loading strain clearly indicate that the damage is accumulated along the interphase until a catastrophic failure of composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the interphase is the key factor of composite performance, its engineering design (“build-up”) is being under spot of interest from both academia and industry. Properties of the interphase should be tailored on the basis of various parameters such as the locally prevailing stress field, possible environmental attack, service temperature, etc. Moreover, considering the fact that the dominating failure mode in fibre-reinforced polymer is debonding under transverse (to fibres) component of loading, its early detection and even its healing are highly desired. In order to early monitor internal microcracks of a material immense efforts have been made over the last decades. Experiments have been reported on embedding optical fibres, piezoelectric sensors/actuators as well as conductive fillers in polymer to checks the variations of time-frequency, acoustic emission, Raman band shift signals and so on[1–5].

Nature is a school for scientists and engineers [6-10]. Learning from nature has long been a source of bio-inspiration for human beings [11-17]. In recent years, a great deal of work has been devoted to fabricating multiscale structures for function integration through the biomimetic or bio-inspired approach. It is desirable to develop bioinspired ‘smart’ coatings on traditional fibres (i.e., glass or carbon fibres — the most commonly used for micro-diameter-scale reinforcements) with autonomic functionalities and abilities for *in-situ* mechanical sensing.

Nacre is a typical organic-inorganic nanocomposite material, consisting of predominately brittle inorganic calcium carbonate and a few percent of biomacromolecules in layered brick-and-mortar architecture over several length scales. The well-defined multiscale structures of abalone nacre confer superior mechanical strength and toughness [18]. For nacre, in addition to extraordinary mechanical properties, it possesses structural colour [19]. The laminated nacreous layers play an important role in producing the iridescent colours [20, 21], which can act as one-dimension photonic bandgap structure. The presence of stacks of uniform nacreous layers results in interference effects that contribute to the iridescent colours [22].

Here, we report a simple deposition approach based on fibre oriented capillary flow to deposit graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) onto glass fibre. GNPs, which are a novel two dimension material,

have excellent electrical conductivity. Inspired by the autonomic functionalities of the natural nacre, we show that the overlapping multi-scale GNPs networks on a single glass fibre surface form an excellent electrically conductive laminated architecture, which integrates optic performance and piezoresistive behaviour.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Depositing the nanostructured ‘skin’ onto glass fibres

Alkali-resistant glass fibres (ARG) with an average diameter of 22 μm manufactured at Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V. by a continuous spinning process. We generated GNPs based on a liquid-phase exfoliation graphite method to avoid the inferior effect to electrical conductivity from conventional graphite oxide reduction method [23, 24]. Mixtures of 0.5 g graphite particles and 0.6 g SDBS surfactant are dissolved in 50 g Millipore water. Adding a surfactant to a solvent prior to sonication prevents restacking by adsorbing to the graphene's surface. A stable diffusion of GNPs in aqueous solution was in turn achieved through the bath sonication (up to 30 hours) and centrifugation process (4000 rpm for 40 minutes). To achieve conducting networks with homogeneous and continuous distribution of carbon nanoparticles (GNPs) on the glass fibre surface, a layer-by-layer self-assembly approach was developed. The glass fibres were placed on a glass slide with separated distance of a few tens of micrometres, and then a droplet GNP solution was dropped onto the glass slide and the imbedded fibres in the solution were coated with GNPs as water evaporated until the solution was dried at 60 °C. As the water evaporates, layer-by-layer self-assemble onto the glass fibre and in turn form multilayer structures. The coated fibres were washed with Millipore water. Because of the capillary flow mainly on the lower surface of the glass fibre, which faces to the glass slide, the carbon nanoparticles are not equally distributed onto the whole fibre surface by a single step coating process. Then, we repeat the coating and washing process for 5-10 times, so that relative uniform surfaces are obtained. Finally, the fibres were dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C for 8 hours and stored under standardised air-condition ($RH = 50\%$, $T = 23\text{ °C}$) for 15 days before the tests.

2.2 Fabricating the model composite with single fibres

A single fibre was mounted within a dog-bone shaped mould. A commercial DGEBA-based epoxy resin and curing agent (Hexion Specialty Chemicals Stuttgart GmbH) were thoroughly mixed and degassed prior to pouring in the mould as polymer matrix. The samples were isothermally cured at 80 °C for 12 h and then slowly cooled down to room temperature with two type dimensions. One is 10 mm gauge length, 1.5 mm width and 0.3 mm thickness for resistance test and the other is 25 mm gauge length, 2 mm width and 1 mm thickness for optic observing.

2.3 Characterization of Functional Glass Fibres and Composites

The fibre surface morphologies were studied using atomic force microscopy (AFM, a Digital Instruments D3100, USA), scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM Ultra 55, Carl Zeiss SMT AG, Germany), and optical microscope (VH-1000, Keyence Corporation, Japan).

The structure colour of the single fibre/epoxy composite under tensile load was observed with optical microscope (VH-1000, Keyence Corporation, Japan).

The electrical resistance of the single fibre and the single fibre/epoxy composite under tensile load was monitored simultaneously with mechanical stress-strain behaviour. The stress-strain curve was detected by FAVIGRAPH Semiautomatic Equipment (Textechno Company, Germany) with a test velocity at 0.2 mm/min. A Keithley 2001 multimeter with constant test current (10 μA /700 nA) was used for electrical resistance measurements; the ends of the samples and test grips were painted with silver paste in order to form an ohmic contact.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nanostructured Surface of Glass Fibre

Firstly, we attempt to produce GNPs with the lowest number of defects and highest electron mobility. Surfactant-aided liquid-phase sonication [23] is optimised and used for graphite exfoliation.

A stable dark-grey colloidal dispersion is obtained, where GNPs are separated from graphite flakes by prolonged sonication and centrifugation in aqueous solution at ambient temperature. A simple overlapping nanoparticle method based on fibre oriented capillary flow for depositing GNPs onto electrically insulating glass fibre surface to form an continuous electrically conducting skin. Consequently, we observed overall uniform overlapping GNP layers with an ordered arrangement of nanostructure on the glass fibre surface (Figure 1a, b), which result in the colour changes from light grey to dark grey. The nanostructured surface shown in AFM image (Figure 1c) is interestingly similar to the skin coverings of vertebrates, i.e. fishes with multilayers of overlapping tough scales providing a protective layer against physical/chemical attack.

Interestingly, the GNPs coated glass fibres show structure colour. As shows in Figure 3a, we observe the GNP-glass fibre shows red colour at the centre of the fibre under the reflection light condition. The structure colour results from the interference of light within a concentrically-layered architecture layers. As mentioned above, the GNPs we prepared which are lamellar structure with varied size from nano to micro scale to form ordered arrangement of nanostructure onto glass fibre surface. This multilayer architecture is expected to show optic performance and piezoresistive behaviour.

Figure 1. Morphology of GNPs coated single glass fibre. a) SEM image of a selected area, scale bar: 4 μm ; b) SEM image, scale bar: 400 nm; c) AFM image a selected area, scale bar: 1 μm).

3.2 Single fibre for mechanical sensing

We investigated whether our conducting GNP-glass fibre is sufficient to show similar piezoresistivity for strain sensing as CNT-glass fibre [25, 26]. The correlation of electrical resistance change $\Delta R/R_0$, mechanical stress σ and strain ε was examined to evaluate the piezoresistive behaviour of GNP-glass fibres under stress up to fracture (Fig.4). We found that the fractional resistance increase ($\Delta R/R_0$) of the fibre increases approximately linearly with tensile strain, which shows very similar behaviour as the CNT-glass fibre and can also be empirically described as:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{GF} \frac{\Delta R}{R_o} + \varepsilon_o \quad (1)$$

where R_o is the initial resistance of the specimen without applying stress, $\Delta R = R - R_o$ is the resistance change, and the parameter, ε_o , refers to the initial strain for piezoresistivity effect of multilayers of GNPs. GF is the strain sensitivity factor (or known as gage factor), i.e., the relative change of resistance to the mechanical strain of strain gage.

In general, the significant resistance change of GNPs on our glass fibre surface can be attributed to not only the stress dependent resistivity of the GNP geometrical structure, but also the stress dependent change of GNP–GNP interspace, contact area and density (junction point per unit volume), as well as associated tunnelling resistance. It should be noted that only below the very small strain level, $\varepsilon_o \approx 0.1\%$, the GNP structure could not be changed recognizably and the main part of GNPs on fibre surface does not undergo mechanical stress. In other words, the onset strain for piezoresistivity effect is extremely low in comparison with other sensors, so that the single GNP–glass fibre has high sensitivity even under small strain level. It is also important to notice that the final abrupt change in resistance at fibre break implies that the single GNP–glass fibre is able to *in-situ* sensing of damage in real composites at micrometre scale.

Further insight into our single fibre sensing ability was gained from the response to cyclic tensile loading. The repeatability of the piezoresistive behaviour for a single GNP–glass fibre was checked under a cyclic tension condition. Figure 2b shows the typical correlation of $\Delta R/R_o$, stress and strain of MWCNT-coated cellulose fibre under stress to a fixed strain of 1.0 %. The $\Delta R/R_o$ increases linearly upon first tensile loading and then decreases linearly upon unloading to a level above the initial zero value, the same as that for fibre strain. This indicates that a reversible deformation of GNP–glass fibre occurred under the tensile stress, leading to the reversible change of the CNT networks coated on the surface. Reloading causes a small variation of $\Delta R/R_o$, and the subsequent cycles show relatively constant electrical resistance change with a small difference, indicating good reversibility and repeatability. It is noted that all of the $\Delta R/R_o$ show a highly linear change with almost the same slope upon tensile stress loading. These impressive characteristics indicate that our GNP–glass fibres are perfect for use as strain sensors. Thus, these sensory fibres can be woven together with other fibres for smart textiles and wearable technology, for example to be used to monitor the motion of muscles and limbs for rehabilitative and telemedicine applications. Moreover, our GNP–glass fibres can be used as integrated sensors or surface-mounted strain gauges to monitor crack initiation/propagation and strain/stress in different composite structures.

Figure 2. Performance of an *in-situ* single fibre sensor. (a) The fractional resistance increase $\Delta R/R_o$ (blue) and linear regression (grey line) of an individual single GNP–glass fibre during static tensile stress (dashed line) up to the fibre fracture. (b) The sensor response to cyclic tensile loading. The variation of electrical resistance with tensile strain/stress in a single fibre.

3.3 Structure colour tuning

As mentioned above, our nano size GNPs form novel multilayer architecture structure on glass fibre surface, the GNP-glass fibre shows structure colour. So we wonder whether our GNP-glass fibre shows structure colour while it embedded in epoxy resin and what will the interphase of GNP-glass fibre with epoxy show during tensile process. As Figure 3b shows, a tensile force along the fibre axis leads to a compression perpendicular to the GNP-glass fibre/epoxy, causing a reduction of the thickness of GNP deposited layer and the epoxy resin. During the tensile process, the thickness and the overlapping structure of GNP layers are changed. So we observe the reflection band shows blue shifts, from red to green, as the stress increases under the reflection light condition. Due to the elongation rate of epoxy is small (less than 7 %), we can hardly observed the structure colour tuned throughout the whole visible spectrum. The glass fibre with overlapping GNP skin provides us a novel way to combine the mechanical and optical properties together for applications in mechanically tuneable light guides or optical strain sensing. In addition, this way makes the glass fibre, which is a tradition fibre reinforcement material, a versatile novel material for smart, colour-dynamic textiles.

Figure 3. Optical microscopic observation of the structure colour on: a) a single GNP-glass fibre and b) a glass fibre embedded in epoxy resin. As the tensile stress increase, the structure colour tuning from red to green (blue shift). All scale bars, 20 μm .

3.4 Single fibre/epoxy composite for mechanical sensing

Figure 4a characterizes the piezoresistive response of the composite with a single GNP-glass fibre to the external loading, the electrical resistance monotonously increases with the applied strain, behaving like a variable resistor, but the slope of relative resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$) curve is varied with typical four stages. At the first stage, the relative electrical resistance nearly doesn't increase to strain up to approximately 0.5 %, caused by the multilayer structure formed electrically conducting networks in the interphase. At higher strains, the relative electrical resistance increases almost linearly proportional to strain up to approximately 2.0 %, caused by dimensional change of GNPs networks in the interphase. At the third step, the resistance-strain curve shows several different ranges jumping, as the red cycle selected area shown in Figure 4a, then exponentially proportional increases to strain, suggesting an irreversible resistance transition, associated with extensive concentration of stresses in interphases, increase of GNP-GNP interspace and loss of contact points. At the fourth stage, owing to the initiation and growth of microcracks in composite, the GNP networks nearby are completely disconnected and the resistance jumps to "infinity" (out of measurable range) at a strain of 6.0 %. Finally, the microcracks continue to propagate leading to the fracture of composite at a strain of about 6.1 %. The micromechanisms of damage in composites have been extensively studied for decades and

the interphase has always been recognized as a key region in the failure process. In our composites, the electric current only passes through the interphase region and both the fibre and the surrounding matrix remain electrically insulating, thereby the resistance change with stress could indicate the interphase destroy mechanism. As a consequence, the unique ability for detecting microcracks in an interphase using a GNP-glass fibre sensor is highlighted, whichever fibre or matrix breaks first.

To further investigate the response of in situ sensor to the interphase damage process, we monitored the resistance variation of the single fibre composite under cyclic loading three times with progressively increasing the strain peaks from 1 % to 5 % (Figure 4b). The relatively large difference in deformation among each cycle highlights the accumulation of damage, which gives insight into the mechanism of resistance change. Clearly, when the peak of strain in the cycles is less than 2.0 % (in the range of linear stage, as aforementioned and shown in Figure 4a), the variation of resistance closely follows the strain which returns to the original point after unloading. However, the strain exceeds the value of linear stage, the value of resistance and the curve of strain increase while stress is 0 in spite of they reach nearly equally high values while the stress reach the high value, suggesting the occurrence of permanent structural deformation/damage of GNP networks caused by microcracks of interphase.

Figure 4. Performance of *in-situ* sensor of a single fibre/epoxy composite. (a) Simultaneous change of electrical resistance and tensile stress as a function of tensile strain for a single fibre/epoxy composite. (b) The sensor response to cyclic tensile loading. The variation of electrical resistance with progressive increase of peak values of tensile strain/stress in a single fibre/epoxy composite.

4 Summary

We have demonstrated that GNP-glass fibres were able to detect and make use of microcracks as real-time in situ sensors for the sensitive controlling of microsystems. Our experiments suggest an integration of optic performance and piezoresistive behaviour to realise strain sensor for traditional fibre reinforcement composites.

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